

SELF-CONTROL AND ENDURANCE AND UNIQUE TAEKWONDO TECHNIQUES,
TRAINING AND ITS IMPACT ON THE STUDENT'S SELF-AWARENESS

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Abstract: the article reveals the principles of taekwondo - respect (politeness), Honesty, perseverance (patience), self-control (self-control), indomitable spirit. Taekwondo provides the necessary minimum of physical activity. Teaches internal discipline and lays the foundations of morality. Has a developed ideological system based on traditional values? Taekwondo is characterized by high repetitions and little resistance to overcome. This develops flexible, thin and long muscles. Such muscles are located closer to the vessels and increase overall endurance. All workouts are accompanied by systematic warming up of muscles and ligaments.

Key words: *taekwondo/ work of a coach/ physical education/ training/ teaching methods/ sports training/ training.*

САМООБЛАДАНИЮ И ВЫНОСЛИВОСТИ И УНИКАЛЬНЫЕ ПРИЕМЫ
ТАЭКВОНДО, ТРЕНИРОВКА И ЕГО ВЛИЯНИЕ НА САМОСОЗНАНИЕ
ШКОЛЬНИКА

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Аннотация: в статье раскрываются принципы таэквондо - почтительность (вежливость), Честность, настойчивость (терпение), самообладание (самоконтроль), неукротимый дух. Тхэквондо дает необходимый минимум физической активности. Приучает к внутренней дисциплине и закладывает основы нравственности. Обладает развитой идейной системой, основанной на традиционных ценностях. Тхэквондо характеризуется большим числом повторений и небольшим сопротивлением, которое нужно преодолеть. Это развивает гибкую, тонкую и длинную мускулатуру. Такие мышцы располагаются ближе к сосудам и увеличивают общую выносливость. Все тренировки сопровождаются систематическим разогревом мышц и связок.

Ключевые слова: *таэквондо/ работа тренера/ физическая культура/ тренировка/ методика обучения/ спортивные тренировки/ обучение.*

Taekwondo provides the necessary minimum of physical activity. Teaches internal discipline and lays the foundations of morality. Has a developed ideological system based on traditional values. Exercises develop flexibility, dexterity and coordination. Taekwondo, also known as taekwondo, is a Korean martial art. A characteristic feature is the active use of legs in combat; both for strikes and for defensive actions. The word "taekwondo" is made up of three Korean words: [tae] "to trample" + [kwon] "fist" + [do] "path, method, teaching, tao." The philosophy of this martial art is complete self-control, resolving conflicts peacefully and self-defense without the use of weapons. Taekwondo for children teaches children self-control and endurance, and unique techniques allow you to neutralize the enemy with one blow.

Taekwondo is characterized by high repetitions and little resistance to overcome. This develops flexible, thin and long muscles. Such muscles are located closer to the vessels and

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increase overall endurance. All workouts are accompanied by systematic warming up of muscles and ligaments. Taekwondo is great for adults to start with - those who have practiced before and want to get back into shape, or those who have not been into the sport. When performing physical exercises, part of the motor action; movement of the human body as a whole relative to its environment (environment, support, physical bodies) or some of its parts relative to others, as well as mechanical movement of sports equipment. Taekwondo is a martial art that came to us from Korea. The main feature of this sport is the use of legs in combat. Karate is a Japanese martial art. It is based on the strength and accuracy of strikes, as well as defense technique. Taekwondo is a Korean martial art. It also emphasizes striking accuracy and defensive techniques, but also includes numerous foot techniques.

First and foremost: taekwondo is about "high" kicks, jumps and step-ups. This requires excellent stretching, coordination and even elements of acrobatics. Actually, this is the basis for training young athletes, who can begin training even at preschool age. Taekwondo uses various parts of the body as the athlete's "weapons". The hands, elbows, feet and knees are used to a greater extent. The name of the impact point is that part of them that delivers the impact impulse into the affected area of the enemy's body.

Taekwondo is a relatively young sport. In the form in which it is known today, it began to exist in 1955. Taekwondo developed in Korea. It differs in that during the wrestling process there is an emphasis on jumping or high kicks.

To make it easier to understand the terminology, you need to understand what the levels of blows are called: olgul - top level, momtong - middle level. And also, the directions: up - forward, yop - sideways, tweet - back. Punching is called chirigi and chigi in Korean.

When studying the practical section in the 1st year of study, much attention was paid to the main types of movements - walking, running, jumping, climbing, necessary for the development of coordination and range of motion of body parts; simple exercises were used in pairs and groups to develop a sense of distance. The classes were aimed at developing the correct algorithm for constructing movement; for this, special importance is attached to the correct execution of basic warm-up exercises in a strictly defined sequence: light running, warming up joints with rotational movements, flexibility and stretching exercises, exercises for coordination of movements, speed and speed exercises. strength qualities - in the implementation of which the main thing is to develop the correct amplitude and tempo of simple movements (running, jumping, etc.). These exercises also lay the basic coordination abilities necessary for mastering the basic stances.

Therefore, after an initial course of exercises (1-2 months), consisting of the listed basic motor actions, it is necessary to add exercises for mastering basic stances to the training. In this case, a game method is used, where students imitate historical characters from folk tales. It is advisable to slowly and gradually increase the number of racks studied. After mastering 4-5 stances, you need to gradually begin learning simple movements in these stances. As you master the program and increase the load related to special exercises for studying stances, it is also necessary to gradually reduce the load during exercises for the development of basic motor actions.

Taekwondo is a martial art that came to us from Korea. The main feature of this sport is the use of legs in combat. The legs are used not only as a tool for attack and attack, but also as defense. This is how the creator of wrestling, Choi Hong Hee, spoke about his brainchild.

When studying, there are 5 principles - respect (politeness), Honesty, perseverance (patience), self-control (self-control), indomitable spirit.

Reverence is an unwritten law recommended by ancient teachers and sages of the East for human improvement and for building a more harmonious society. In building their character, all Taekwondo practitioners must practice the following manifestations of respect, including them in the training process as its mandatory elements:

Develop a spirit of mutual respect. Get rid of your bad habits and put up with the bad habits of other people.

Maintain an atmosphere of justice and humanism around yourself.

Maintain a hierarchy in the relationship between students and the instructor, between beginners and older students, between seniors and juniors in age and social status. When communicating with people, behave in accordance with their accepted rules of etiquette.

Respect the position of other people and recognize their strengths.

Behave honestly and openly with others.

Refrain from accepting or giving gifts in all cases where this could be misinterpreted.

Every person should be able to distinguish true from false, and if they are wrong, honestly admit it. The following are examples that illustrate this lack of honesty:

Discrepancy between words and deeds. Attempts to obtain a higher belt through undignified means. Using sawed boards to demonstrate the impact force. The desire to get a belt to demonstrate one's superiority over other people.

One of the secrets of becoming a master is patient and persistent overcoming all difficulties. Happiness and success most often go to persistent people. In order to achieve anything, you need to set a goal and patiently achieve it.

Self-control is extremely important both in the training room and in everyday life. Losing self-control during sparring can lead to very serious consequences for both opponents. Uncooperative behavior within a team is often a manifestation of poor self-control.

Those who practice Taekwon-Do must be honest and sincere. When faced with injustice, they must act decisively, without fear, showing an indomitable spirit, no matter who opposes them or how many opponents there are.

LITERATURES USED:

1. Тураев, М. М. (2022). Оздоровительная физическая культура её основы и инновационные технологии. *Science and Education*, 3(4), 1102-1108.

2. Тураев, М. М. Образование и воспитание в сфере физической культуры-особенности повышения эффективности использования национальных ценностей. *Центр научных публикаций (buxdu.uz)*, 8(8).

3. Тураев, М. М. (2022, November). Организация проектных технологий на уроках физической культуры: 10.53885/edinres. 2022.61. 66.124 Тураев Махмуд Мухамедович Бухарский государственный университет, преподаватель. In *Научно-практическая конференция* (pp. 975-978).

4. Тураев, М. М. (2024). Сравнительная педагогика физической культуры, отрасль знания спорта и учебная дисциплина. *Science and Education*, 5(2), 335-340.

5. Тураев, М. М. (2024). Педагогическая технология в спортивной гимнастике, системы имитационного моделирования. *Science and Education*, 5(1), 332-337.

6. Тураев, М. М., Баймурадов, Р. С., & Файзиев, Я. З. (2020). Интерактивные методы физического воспитания в вузах. *Педагогическое образование и наука*, (3), 132-135.

7. Хамраев, И. Т., Курбанов, Д. И., & Тураев, М. М. (2021). Принципы современной педагогической подготовки. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(2), 899-907.
8. Тураев, М. М. (2021). Методы преподавания физического образования и их важные аспекты. *Проблемы науки*, (2 (61)), 35-37.
9. Тураев, М. М. (2021). Повышение эффективности физического воспитания студентов с помощью компьютерных технологий. *Вестник науки и образования*, (5-3 (118)), 99-102.
10. MM Turaev, BJ Boltayeva, SJ Razokova. **The importance of physical education and physical culture at schools**. *Вестник науки и образования* 1 (2-2 (122)), 34-37
11. Тураев, М. М. Теория и методика физической культуры. Учебное пособие, 1(1), 220.
12. Тураев, М. М. Методы преподавания социального образования и их важные аспекты. *Проблемы науки*, 35-37.
13. Маъмуров, Б. Б., & Тураев, М. М. (2023). Актуальные проблемы подготовки специалистов физического воспитания и спорта в современных условиях. In *Проблемы и перспективы развития спортивного образования, науки и практики* (pp. 134-142).
14. Тураев, М. М. (2022, November). Организация проектных технологий на уроках физической культуры: 10.53885/edinres. 2022.61. 66.124 Тураев Махмуд Мухамедович Бухарский государственный университет, преподаватель. In *Научно-практическая конференция* (pp. 975-978).
15. Баймурадов, Р. С., Файзиев, Я. З., & Тураев, М. М. (2019). Психологический анализ личности спортсмена. *Педагогическое образование и наука*, (6), 144-148.
16. Тураев, М. М. (2024). Сравнительная педагогика физической культуры, отрасль знания спорта и учебная дисциплина. *Science and Education*, 5(2), 335-340.
17. MM Тураев, ЭЮ Исломов. Организация и проведение оздоровительных занятий для людей пожилого возраста. *Физическая культура. Рекреация. Спорт*, 470-476
18. Тураев, М. М. (2024). Педагогическая технология в спортивной гимнастике, системы имитационного моделирования. *Science and Education*, 5(1), 332-337.
19. M Тураев. Important factors for the organization of medical groups in physical education. Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz) 8 (8)
20. M Тураев. **Содержание процесса организации оздоровительных занятий для людей пожилого возраста**. Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz) 7 (7)
21. M Тураев. **Actual problems of teaching physical education at school**. Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. uz) 23 (23)
22. MM Turayev, BJQ Boltayeva. **Og'ma xulq-atvor o'rganish mahsuli sifatida**. *Science and Education* 3 (4), 1694-1701
23. MM Тураев. Теория и методика физической культуры. *Вестник Бухарского государственного университета* 1, 1 - 276
24. АБ Жураев. Обучения к нагрузкам физической подготовки как деятельность подготовке школьников. *Science and Education* 5 (2), 574-579
25. Alibek Botirovich Jo'rayev (2024). Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida harakatli o'yinlar orqali jismoniy sifatlarni rivojlantirish (kurash)
26. Рахмон Равшанович Латипов. . Пиндский журнал культуры, литературы и ELT 3 (3), 42-47

27. Рахмон Равшанович Латипов (2024). Школьная аксиологическая подготовка учителя физической культуры на современном этапе эволюции. *Science and Education*, 5 (1), 299-304.

28. Рахмон Равшанович Латипов (2024). Философия спортивного искусства и образования в подготовке педагога-физической культуры. *Science and Education*, 5 (1), 292-298.

29. Latipov, R., & Ramazanov, M. (2023). Jismoniy madaniyat ta'lim yo'nalishi talabalarini kasbiy pedagogik madaniyatni tarbiyalashda tajriba-sinov ishlarining samaradorlik darajasi. *Молодые ученые*, 1(21), 37–40.

30. К.С. Колдошвич, Л.Р. Равшанович. Педагогические, психологические основы дентологической подготовки студентов высших учебных заведений (физическая культура). *Американский журнал языка, грамотности и обучения в области STEM-образования* 1 (2...

